

THE ELIZABETHAN WORLD AND ITS LEGACY

All the News – Members Only

by Angela Ranson

About the Newsletter

This newsletter aims to bring together work by scholars and enthusiasts. While there is no requirement for contributions to be written by people who have studied the Elizabethan world in an academic context, we do intend to include only legitimate, well-researched content. Thus, this newsletter will be an opportunity for our members to share the topics that interest them, as well as advertise upcoming events and projects.

About the Society

We are pleased to report that since our launch in December 2015, we have grown from six to 160 members. They include early career researchers, independent scholars, established lecturers and people who study the Elizabethan world on their own. In addition, our members come from all over the world, from Algeria to South Korea to Wales.

About the Conference

We are pleased to welcome Dr. Tracy Borman to our programme. Dr. Borman will be our keynote speaker on 18 November, speaking on the private life of Elizabeth I. She is a joint curator of the Historic Royal Palaces and the author of *Elizabeth's Women*.

Discourse

Of the Gloriana Society

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early 1560s with a close-fitting decorated cap and veil. A loose gown, based on a portrait of the late 1560s, gave the idea for an early 'Sindy' doll now over fifty years old, to be dressed in such a gown over embroidered, tied-on sleeves and kirtle, the outfit being completed with a padded, feathered cap.

As my understanding of historical costume grew by actually making such items, it proved helpful in less practical forms of research. Indeed, it has influenced my current study of the portrayal of Margaret Clifford, both during her lifetime and after. She was Queen Elizabeth's cousin, and a claimant to the throne after the Grey sisters.

Joy Childs' publications focus mainly on the history of Derbyshire. She published Dorothy: the Romantic Story of

Dorothy Vernon of Haddon Hall in 1984, and contributed an article entitled 'A Stranger in the Dales' to Yesterday's Yorkshire in 1991. She has also published three historical novels under the name Marie Sandeford.

Sir Robert Shirley: Adventurer and Diplomat in the Safavids Empire

By Gunay Heydarli

The rise to power of Shah Abbas I (1587-1629) and his outward-looking agenda, epitomized by an energetic foreign policy, created a political and economic environment that attracted keen European interest in Safavids as a land of religious, commercial, and strategic opportunity. The British Museum's director Neil MacGregor, in his foreword to the 274-page exhibition catalogue, compares Shah 'Abbas with his contemporary, Queen Elizabeth I of England. Like Elizabeth I, Shah 'Abbas inherited in difficult circumstances an unstable country that had recently redefined its religion and was surrounded and threatened by powerful enemies.

This was an era when Britons and Muslims first met each other and learned about each other's customs, religion, laws and society. From the Mediterranean that encompassed Morocco and the Ottoman Empire, the initial British experience of Islam rapidly moved eastward, toward Safavids and Mughal India- the two most powerful Islamic civilizations. Realizing the potential in the markets of these empires, both for export and import, Britons set out

to get rich by exploring trade routes and negotiating agreements. The first and perhaps best known Europeans who visited Safavids during Shah ' Abbas's reign were the Englishmen Sir Anthony Shirley and his brother Sir Robert. In 1598, at the apparent bidding of the Earl of Essex, they traveled to Qazvin.

Shah 'Abbas treated both brothers with much hospitality and paid them great deal of attention. He sent Anthony Shirley back to Europe along with the Persian ambassador Huseyn Ali Beg, Nicolao de Melo, in late April 1599. Anthony Shirley took with

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him letters of friendship written by Shah 'Abbas to at least nine European leaders, including Queen Elizabeth I and Philipp III of Spain. Meanwhile, Robert stayed with the Shah. He was just eighteen years old at the time. Shah Abbas appointed him as special lackey and grant him the title of 'Son of Beig'. He always wore Iranian clothing and wore turban in Safavid style on his head, but he put a crusade on the tip of the turban.

Safavid's embassy delegation, headed by Robert Shirley on February 12, 1608 was headed to Europe from the way of Caspian Sea and Russia. In Cracovie they were warmly accepted by Sigismound Vasa,

king of Poland, and Rodelf the Second, king of Germany. Then Robert went to Italy was presented to the pope, who also accepted him warmly and awarded him the title of Conte De Palatin in a magnificent ceremony. From there, Shirley went to Spain and was presented to Philip the Third, who accepted to some suggestions made by Shirley concerning the trade between the two nations and also his provisions sending out Safavid silk from the Hormoz route and India to Europe.

Philip the Third wrote a letter to king Abbas and gave it Robert Shirley and it was promised within that he would soon attack to Ottoman Sultans by the help of the pope and other European commanders. He sent some ships to Ahmar Sea in order to block India's route from which it is sent to Ottoman State. Then Robert Shirley went to England. In 1611, James the First received Robert Shirley in Hampton Court Palace and Shirley granted him the letters by Abbas. James signed a friendly treaty, having the knowledge of the political benefits of relations with Safavids, and then wrote a letter to King Abbas. Also, Shirley was awarded Knight Courtier and Knight degree.

In 1613 Shirley returned to Persia, but he returned to Europe in 1615 and resided at Madrid. In accordance with the political situation, England suddenly started taking an interest in the Safavid state. The Dutch East India Company methodically expelled English merchants from Indonesia while in India trouble emerged with the opening of a trading post in Gujarat. The opening of English trading posts in the Persian Gulf could provide an excellent opportunities for trade

in the East. The idea of moving the silk trade to the road that ran along the Caspian Sea and the Volga to the White Sea and from there to the North Sea began to take on a more and more concrete shape. The English had the right of transit and free trade in Russia, and raising the agreements signed by Robert Shirley on behalf of the Safavid Shah, they became convinced that he had provided benefits for English merchants. In many ways, it predetermined the further successes of Britons in the East, which is why Sir Robert is revered by British historians.

Gunay Heydarli is a PhD student working under the supervision of Professor Yagub Mahmudov in the Department of History at Baku State University. She earned her BA and MS degrees in history from the Baku State University. She is interested in the religious history of the Middle Ages from a cultural perspective: how ideas, values, and relationships were incarnated in symbols, customs, behaviors, and structures. Her current work focuses on Papal "overlordship" of Kings and Kingdoms.

Sir Robert Shirley

The Internal Colonialism Model and Elizabethan Territorial Expansion: A Syncretic Approach

By Dimitra Koutla

This short essay will provide a brief overview of my approach to Elizabethan colonialism, within the context of early modern state formation and the development of the early stages of agrarian capitalism. What I wish to suggest is that Michael Hechter's internal colonialism model of English national development provides a sound methodological framework for the study of the peculiar and unique early English colonialist ventures in Ireland and the New World during the sixteenth century, when compared to continental counterparts.

The difficulty of comparing and contrasting Irish and American plantations and expeditions has thrown into sharp relief the inability of these first entrepreneurs to distinguish between these two contexts, as shown in the analysis of the unique promotional literature of the time. To be more specific, in my study of these texts I have located two motives of the proponents of colonialism. First, we can clearly distinguish the political motive of extending Crown authority and imposing English law in territories that were at the time in an ambiguous relation to the English central government, in an attempt to safeguard national security and territorial integrity. This process of extending the administrative institutions was initiated during Henry VIII's reign with the

assimilation of Wales and Scotland, and the Crown Act of 1542 which declared the Crown's attempt to fully incorporate Ireland into its body politic. The need to safeguard these Celtic borderlands was particularly pronounced during Elizabeth's reign, when her Protestant realm was constantly under the threat of invasion from the Catholic powers of Spain, France, Scotland and the Pope, a threat that materialised with the Spanish Armada in 1588. Simultaneously, English proponents of colonialism, and particularly in this case Sir Walter Raleigh, suggested that the power of the Spanish empire should be dealt with in their New World territories. By establishing a powerful overseas empire, the English could rival the wealth and naval power of the Spanish Emperor, while at the same time magnifying their power by the acquisition of new territories and the establishment of plantations.

The second motive for colonial expansion was equally important, and inextricably linked to the first: namely, the material motive of financial gain, in the context of an agrarian capitalist economy that would flourish in the new plantations. Due to a general food shortage, a consequent rise in the prices of basic agricultural products, and the demographic problem of overpopulation – partly instigated by the dissolution of the monasteries under Henry VIII - plantations were seen as the singularly effective solution that would in one swift stroke solve the problem of lack of land and overpopulation. The vast expanses of land in Ireland and the

Americas, which the English claimed were populated though underutilised, would provide the means by which surplus would be extracted through the capitalist exploitation of the land, by the application of new methods of tillage, crop rotation and land enclosures. Territories in Ireland would be acquired by the method of escheating, where the lands of a landowning Gaelic lord would be confiscated by the Crown after he rebelled and was branded a traitor. The acquisition of lands in the New World did not require such legal justifications, as the English simply argued that the Native Americans were located at an earlier stage of cultural development and did not have the means to exploit the land to its full potential, and thus had no legal

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ownership of it.

What is then the internal colonialism model, and what does its application have to offer to the study of Elizabethan colonialism? Hechter defines internal colonialism as 'the political incorporation of a culturally distinct group by the core' which is seen to 'dominate the periphery politically and exploit it materially' (*Internal Colonialism* 9n; 32). Hechter accepts the possibility that the 'simultaneous overseas expansion of Western European states [and] similar

thrusts into peripheral hinterlands' that peaked in the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries had been motivated by the same forces, and indeed, my research has shown this hypothesis to be true. The appeal for this model is, on the one hand, that it allows us to accept that the initial motives behind internal and overseas colonialist projects were the same, while on the other hand, it explains the huge divergence between the history of colonialism in Ireland and North America during the centuries that followed. This evolution over time of these initially similar waves of territorial expansion can be distinguished between either national, or imperial, depending on whether the regime achieves legitimacy over the course of several generations.

This model can help solve the paradoxical status of Ireland during Elizabeth's reign, and eliminate the need to make any absolute statements in favour of one of the two competing positions, the well-known kingdom vs colony debate. By placing Elizabethan colonialism within the context of early modern nation-building and the emergent practices of agrarian capitalism, we can clearly see that there was no differentiation between methods that imposed State law, disseminated royal authority, and reduced Ireland and the New World territories to a colonial status. As I am arguing in my dissertation, the sixteenth century was a formative period for colonialism, capitalism and nation-state formation, hence the need for a syncretic and nuanced model of analysis.